

THE RESPONSIBILITIES OF PREVENTION INSPECTORS IN PREVENTING OFFENSES WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF FAMILY LIFE

Nazarov Ilkhom Alimovich

Senior lecturer of the Department of Special and Professional
Disciplines at the Institute of Advanced Training, Lieutenant Colonel
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Abstract: The significance of this article lies in outlining the tasks of Prevention Inspectors as defined in laws and regulations, as well as highlighting current problems and shortcomings in preventing offenses within the context of family life

Keywords: Family and domestic offenses, "Causes of commission," "Family prevention program," "sector working group"

Family is a solid foundation of society that has been shaped over centuries, a powerful institution ensuring societal development, and the comprehensive well-being of society depends on the peace, tranquility, and stability of families. Several reforms are being implemented to preserve each family, maintain a healthy moral environment within them, and foster a sense of kindness and compassion

Despite the implementation of a number of preventive measures to prevent crimes between spouses, parents and children, brothers and sisters, and mothers-in-law and daughters-in-law, offenses within the context of family life, that is, crimes committed within family relationships, continue to occur.

Family-life relations are personal relations between husband and wife, parents and children, bride and groom and father-in-law and mother-in-law, father-in-law and mother-in-law and sister-in-law, grandparents and grandchildren, brothers and sisters, adopted and adopted, between neighbors and similar relatives, primarily related to marriage, blood kinship or family and other ties.

Family-life offenses are a combination of concepts such as "family," "life," "family-life relations," "family-life sphere," and "offence."

Currently, the following can be attributed to the commission of offenses within the framework of family life

unhealthy spiritual and psychological environment in the family;

weakness or weakness of spiritual and moral education in the family;

antisocial behavior that is present in a family member (s);

material shortage and difficulties in the family;

alcohol dependence of a family member (s);

unjustified (excessive) jealousy in the family, male and female infidelity;

there are violations following premature marriage and inappropriate interference in young family relationships

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-371 "On the Prevention of Offenses" dated May 14, 2014, and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-60 "On the Strategy for the Development of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" dated January 28, 2022, provide for the strengthening of the spiritual foundation of the family as one of the directions in preventing this type of crime. One of the goals of our reforms in the judicial and

legal sphere is to guarantee citizens, including the family, peace and tranquility, early prevention of crimes and offenses in all spheres of family life.

On the assigned administrative territory, the prevention inspector performs the following tasks for the prevention of offenses within the framework of family life: 1.

- working with families of this category of persons in conducting preventive interviews with persons under administrative supervision and preventive registration, prone to committing offenses;

- development of the "Family Prevention" program for conducting preventive work with socially vulnerable families;

A "family prevention program" is a comprehensive implementation of crime prevention at the family level, a program of social, legal, medical, economic, financial, pedagogical, psychological, and other measures, taking into account the family environment, the relationships of family members, the social and material situation of the family, and the impact of common family problems on the upbringing and education of children.

- conducting legal campaigns (round tables, meetings, lectures, etc.) in families on topical topics, as well as bringing to the attention of the population, especially young people, the essence and content of newly adopted legislative acts;

- studying and analyzing the causes of crimes and offenses committed by the family and the conditions that made them possible;

- assessment of the impact of the negative family environment on the criminogenic situation;

- contacting the sector working group with identified problems in the family and proposals for their solution.

If the preventive inspector's cooperation with the mahalla seven plays a key role in the early prevention of offenses occurring within the framework of family life, and if work is organized in cooperation with the seven in identifying and solving the problems of conflict families, intentional murder, suicide, intentional infliction of light, moderate and severe bodily harm, torture, threat of murder or use of violence, insult, hooliganism will be prevented within the framework of family-living relations, and this will play an important role in the formation of a sense of compassion between

Used references:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-371 "On the Prevention of Offenses" dated May 14, 2014.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-60 dated January 28, 2022, "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026."
3. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020; Resolution No. PP-4602 dated February 18, 2020, "On Organizing the Activities of the Ministry of Mahalla and Family Support of the Republic of Uzbekistan."
4. Resolution No. 3 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 4, 2020, "On Measures to Improve the System of Protecting Women from Oppression and Violence."